

Appendix 1. Research Questionnaire

Dear Sir/Madam,
Managers/Owners of Food Sector SMEs in Riau Province

With due respect, we kindly request your willingness to spare some time to complete this research questionnaire on Sustainable Business Performance. This questionnaire is solely intended for research purposes; therefore, your honest and sincere responses will greatly contribute to the objectivity of the research results. We assure you that all responses will be kept strictly confidential.

We truly appreciate your attention and cooperation.

Sincerely,

Head of Research Team
Tengku Firli Musfar

Respondent Profile

Item	Response
Respondent's Name	
Company Name	
Business Address	
Phone Number	
Age	
Gender	
Highest Education	
Years of Business Operation	
Business Specialization	
Total Assets	
Annual Turnover	
Number of Employees	

Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements using the 5-point Likert scale:

1 = Strongly Disagree (SD), 2 = Disagree (D), 3 = Neutral (N), 4 = Agree (A), 5 = Strongly Agree (SA)

Item Code	Statement	1 (SD)	2 (D)	3 (N)	4 (A)	5 (SA)
SBP1	Our profits have increased over the last three years.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
SBP2	We have become more efficient in our business activities.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
SBP3	We have improved our working methods to be more effective.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
SBP4	The surrounding community sympathizes with our company.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
SBP5	Our company provides benefits to the surrounding community.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
SBP6	We provide more assistance to the surrounding community.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
SBP7	Several parties appreciate our efforts to protect the environment.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
SBP8	We are active in saving the environment.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
SBP9	We are more efficient in the use of resources.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GE01	We consider environmental impact when making decisions.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GE02	We always try to find more environmentally friendly ways in our business.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GE03	We proactively initiate good actions for the environment.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

GEO4	We strive to take advantage of business opportunities aligned with environmental preservation.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GI1	We use materials that do not pollute the environment.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GI2	We use raw materials as efficiently as possible.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GI3	Our products can be recycled, reused, or are biodegradable.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GI4	We recycle our production waste.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GI5	We run our business operations efficiently.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GMS1	We do not use parts of protected animals.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GMS2	The materials we use are safe for consumers.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GMS3	Our products have advantages because they are environmentally friendly.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GMS4	We use environmentally friendly packaging.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GMS5	We set higher prices due to our commitment to the environment.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GMS6	We believe consumers are willing to pay more for environmentally friendly products.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GMS7	Our products are easy to find and purchase.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GMS8	We also sell products online.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GMS9	We try to choose fuel-efficient vehicles for product delivery.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GMS10	We promote the use of environmentally	<input type="checkbox"/>				

	friendly materials.					
GMS11	We highlight environmental awareness in our promotions.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GMS12	We do a lot of promotion through digital media.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
GMS13	The materials we use in promotion support environmental preservation.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
ER1	We are committed to preserving water resources.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
ER2	We strive to reduce air pollution.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
ER3	We are careful in handling hazardous and toxic materials (B3).	<input type="checkbox"/>				
ER4	We are responsible for proper waste management.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
EC1	We cooperate with companies or partners that have an environmentally friendly commitment.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
EC2	We prefer products that use environmentally friendly packaging.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
EC3	We are aware of and understand our responsibility to protect and preserve the environment.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
EC4	We always follow information related to environmental issues.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Thank you very much for your time and willingness to participate in this research. Your contribution is highly valuable for the success of this study.